

EXECUTIVE FUNCTION AND ACADEMIC SUCCESS OF TRIBAL ADOLESCENTS: AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

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Abstract

The major intent of the study was to identify the relationship between executive function and academic success of tribal adolescents belonging to the Jharkhand state of India and to examine the relationship between academic success and the executive function of tribal adolescent boys and girls separately and as a whole. The study comes under survey design of descriptive type of research. The investigator collected data from 378 students from different districts of Jharkhand using a stratified sampling technique. The data were collected by using a standardized scale on executive function, and for academic success, 10th-grade adolescents' academic scores on their 9th-grade examinations were taken into consideration. The results of the study revealed that the relationship between executive function and academic success of tribal adolescents of Jharkhand is significantly positive but negligible. However, the study also revealed that the academic success of adolescents is not significantly related to either cognitive flexibility or the inhibition control component of executive function, but the dimension of working memory has a significant relationship with academic success. Further, the study also shows that there is a positive relationship between executive function and academic success among tribal adolescent boys, but the reverse result was reported in the case of the girls. Therefore, it can be

recommended that the teachers are expected to focus on different dimensions of executive function i.e. cognitive flexibility, working memory, and inhibition control to exert a healthy lifestyle among the students that is expected to enhance the executive function, academic success, and the overall well-being.

Keywords: *Executive Function, Academic Success, Tribal Adolescents, Secondary School Adolescents*

Introduction

Executive function refers to a set of cognitive abilities enabling individuals to control thoughts and behaviors to achieve goals. It includes cognitive flexibility, working memory, and inhibitory control. These abilities develop significantly from early childhood through adolescence into early adulthood (Zelazo & Carlson, 2020). In contemporary education, the significance of executive function—comprising cognitive flexibility, working memory, and inhibitory control—has become increasingly evident in students' success. Schools are adopting strategies to enhance these skills, which are vital for managing tasks, organizing, paying attention, and remembering instructions. This comprehensive approach underscores that overall learning outcomes depend on cognitive development, sharpening critical thinking, analysis, decision-making, and other essential life skills. Cognitive flexibility involves thinking about multiple concepts simultaneously and adapting to new situations. Working memory allows temporary storage and manipulation of information for reasoning and decision-making. Inhibitory control enables resisting impulses to choose actions aligned with goals (Diamond, 2006; Miyake et al., 2000).

Academic success encompasses various forms, including grades, personal development, and achievements. It involves student agency, aptitudes, and support types, such as goal-setting, self-control, self-evaluation, motivation, institutional support, and external support (Lynam et al., 2022). Factors influencing academic success include time management, peer relationships, parental engagement, academic self-efficacy, adjustment, motivation, emotional well-being, information availability, socioeconomic status, and language proficiency (Thomas & Maree, 2021). Effective management of these factors is crucial for maximizing productivity and achieving academic goals. Executive function is vital for coordinating cognitive and behavioral activities necessary for academic success (Blair, 2016). Research indicates a positive relationship between executive function and academic success (Bull et al., 2008; Clark et al., 2010; Monette et al., 2011). Training in executive function can enhance the ability to achieve real-world goals like academic success (Gunzenhauser & Nückles, 2021). Cognitive flexibility, working memory, and inhibitory control are significantly correlated with academic success

(Alloway & Alloway, 2010; Espy et al., 2004). Understanding these relationships can inform targeted interventions to improve educational outcomes.

Tribal adolescents in Jharkhand face unique socio-cultural and economic challenges impacting academic performance and executive function development. Understanding these challenges is essential for developing effective educational policies and interventions. This research aims to explore the relationship between executive function and academic success among Jharkhand's tribal adolescents, especially secondary-level students. By examining this link, the study seeks to provide insights for creating inclusive educational strategies that promote diversity, equity, and sustainable development in tribal communities. Despite the recognized importance of executive function in academic success, there is limited research on its impact among Jharkhand's tribal adolescents. This study aims to address this gap by investigating the relationship between executive function and academic success. The findings will inform the development of targeted educational interventions and policies to enhance learning outcomes for tribal adolescents in Jharkhand.

Objectives

1. To explain the relationship between executive functions and academic success among the tribal adolescents of Jharkhand.
2. To identify the specific executive functions that are most strongly associated with academic success among the tribal adolescents of Jharkhand.
3. To examine the relationship executive function and academic of tribal adolescent boys.
4. To examine the relationship between executive function and academic success of tribal adolescent girls.

Hypotheses

1. There will be a statistically significant relationship between executive function and academic success of tribal adolescents of Jharkhand.
2. There will be a significant and positive relationship between cognitive flexibility and the academic success of tribal adolescents.
3. There will be a significant and positive relationship between working memory and the academic success of tribal adolescents.
4. There will be a significant and positive relationship between inhibition control and the academic success of tribal adolescents.
5. There will be a positive relationship between executive function and the academic success of tribal adolescent boys.

6. There will be a positive relationship between executive function and the academic success of tribal adolescent girls.

Methods and Procedure

Research Design: The study aims to understand the relationship between executive function and academic success of tribal adolescents in different secondary schools of Jharkhand. Because of the nature of the study, which demands a thorough investigation, therefore, data collection from a huge sample to conclude with a 0.05 level of significance, the researcher used the survey method of descriptive type of research.

Population and Sample: The population in the present study covers 10th-grade adolescents enrolled in schools in Jharkhand. In the present study, the data has been collected from 10th-grade adolescents i.e., secondary-level students studying in different schools in Jharkhand covering four districts (Jamtara, Giridih, Deoghar, and Dhanbad). The sample size with a 95% confidence level is 378, per the Rao Soft sample size calculator. The study employed stratified proportional sampling since the number of adolescents with a gender-wise breakup has been selected proportionally from different Jharkhand districts or strata.

Tools for Data Collection: The investigator in the study collected data on the variable academic success and executive function of tribal adolescents of Jharkhand using an unpublished scale developed by Rana & Pany (2024). The scale consists of 28 items and covers three dimensions: cognitive flexibility, working memory, and inhibition control. Items 1 to 8 fall under cognitive flexibility, whereas items 9 to 17 fall under working memory, and inhibition control covers items 18 to 28. The reliability coefficient of the scale is 0.88.

Analysis and Interpretation

I. Normality of Distribution of Data on Executive Function and Academic Success

The study aimed to determine the relationship between executive function and academic success among tribal adolescents. Therefore, it was crucial to determine whether the data were normally distributed before using the correlation coefficient. In this context, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov(K-S) normality test was applied to the executive function and academic success score of tribal adolescents and it was found to be normal (p value>.05). Here, it can be said that the sample distribution of the scores is normally distributed.

II. Relationship Between Academic Success and Executive Function of Tribal Adolescents of Jharkhand

The study's first objective was to examine the relationship between executive function and academic success among the tribal adolescents of Jharkhand. In this context, the data

collected from 10th-grade tribal adolescents from different districts of Jharkhand were subjected to finding the significance of the relationship between executive function and academic success of tribal adolescents. The analysis of the data has been presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Executive Function and Academic Success of Tribal Adolescents of Jharkhand

Variable	N	M	σ	r	Sig
Executive Function	378	95.62	9.509	0.128	0.01
Academic Success	378	340.81	49.02		

The mean and S.D. on the executive function were found to be 95.62 and 9.509, respectively, whereas the mean and S.D. on academic success were found to be 340.81 and 49.02, respectively. The correlation coefficient between executive function and academic success among tribal adolescents was 0.128. The results mentioned in Table 1 revealed that there is a negligible relationship between executive function and the academic success of tribal adolescents (Aggarwal, 2004). Further, when tested for their significance with 376 degrees of freedom, the correlation coefficient was found to be significant at 0.01 level. Hence, the hypothesis *“There will be a statistically significant relationship between academic success and executive function of tribal adolescents of Jharkhand”* is accepted and it can be interpreted that there exists a statistically significant relationship between the two variables though such relationship is negligible.

III. Relationship Between Cognitive Flexibility with Academic Success of Tribal Adolescents

The study's second objective was to identify the association between the specific executive functions i.e. cognitive flexibility with academic success among the tribal adolescents of Jharkhand. Their Mean, S.D. and correlation were calculated. A detailed description of the results has been presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Cognitive Flexibility and Academic Success of Tribal Adolescents of Jharkhand

Variable	N	M	σ	r	Sig
Cognitive Flexibility	378	27.62	3.369	0.059	Not
Academic Success	378	340.81	49.02		Significant

The mean and S.D. on cognitive flexibility were found to be 27.62 and 3.369, respectively, whereas the mean and S.D. on academic success were found to be 340.81 and 49.02 respectively. The coefficient of correlation between cognitive flexibility and academic

success of tribal adolescents is found to be 0.059. The results mentioned in Table 2 reveal that there exists a very negligible relationship between cognitive flexibility and academic success of tribal adolescents (Aggarwal, 2004). Further, when tested for their significance with 376 degrees of freedom, the correlation coefficient was found not to be significant. Hence, the hypothesis “*There will be a significant and positive relationship between cognitive flexibility and the academic success of tribal adolescents*” is rejected, and it is interpreted that the relationship is not significant.

IV. Relationship Between Working Memory with Academic Success of Tribal Adolescents

The study's third objective was to identify the specific executive functions, i.e., working memory is most strongly associated with academic success among the tribal adolescents of Jharkhand. A detailed description of the results has been presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Working Memory and Academic Success of Tribal Adolescents of Jharkhand

Variable	N	M	σ	r	Sig
Working Memory	378	30.47	5.154	0.168	0.01
Academic Success	378	340.81	49.02		

The mean and S.D. on working memory were 30.47 and 5.154 respectively, whereas the mean and S.D. on academic success were 340.81 and 49.02 respectively. The coefficient of correlation between working memory and academic success of tribal adolescents is found to be 0.168. The results mentioned in Table 3 reveal that there exists a very negligible relationship between working memory and academic success of tribal adolescents (Aggarwal, 2004). Further, when tested for their significance with 376 degrees of freedom, the correlation coefficient was found to be significant at 0.01 level. Hence, the hypothesis “*There will be a significant and positive relationship between working memory and the academic success of tribal adolescents*” is accepted, and it can be interpreted that there exists a significant positive relationship between the two variables.

V. Relationship Between Inhibition Control with Academic Success of Tribal Adolescents

The study's fourth objective was to identify the relationship between the specific executive functions i.e. inhibition control and academic success of tribal adolescents of Jharkhand. A detailed description of the results has been presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Inhibition Control and Academic Success of Tribal Adolescents of Jharkhand

Variable	N	M	σ	r	Sig
Inhibition Control	378	37.53	5.552	0.028	Not Significant
Academic Success	378	340.81	49.02		

The mean and S.D. on the inhibition control were found to be 37.53 and 5.552 respectively, whereas the mean and S.D. on academic success were found to be 340.81 and 49.02 respectively. The coefficient of correlation between inhibition control and academic success of tribal adolescents was found to be 0.028. The results mentioned in Table 4 reveal that there exists a very negligible relationship between inhibition control and the academic success of tribal adolescents (Aggarwal, 2004). Further, when tested for their significance with 376 degrees of freedom, the correlation coefficient was found not to be significant. Hence, the hypothesis *“There will be a significant and positive relationship between inhibition control and the academic success of tribal adolescents”* is rejected and it can be interpreted that the relationship is not significant between the two variables.

VI. Relationship Between Executive Function and Academic Success of Tribal Adolescent Boys

The study's fifth objective was to identify the relationship between academic success and executive function of tribal adolescent boys. Table 5 reveals the relationship between executive function and academic success of tribal adolescent boys.

Table 5: Executive Function and Academic Success of Tribal Adolescent Boys

Variable	N	M	σ	r	Sig
Executive Function	182	97.66	10.123	0.21	0.01
Academic Success	182	330.78	52.756		

The mean and S.D. of executive function is 97.66 and 10.123 whereas the mean and S.D. of academic success is 330.78 and 52.756 respectively. The correlation between executive function and academic success of tribal adolescent boys is 0.21. Further, when tested for their significance with 180 degrees of freedom, the correlation coefficient was found to be significant at 0.01 level. Hence, the null hypothesis *“There will be a positive relationship between executive function and the academic success of tribal adolescent boys”* is accepted and it can be interpreted that both variables are significantly related.

VII. Relationship Between Executive Function and Academic Success of Tribal Adolescent Girls

The study's sixth objective was to identify the relationship between academic success and executive function of tribal adolescent girls. Table 6 reveals the relationship between executive function and academic success of tribal adolescent girls.

Table 6: Executive Function and Academic Success of Tribal Adolescent Girls

Variable	N	M	σ	r	Sig
Executive Function	196	93.72	8.495	0.131	Not Significant
Academic Success	196	350.13	43.373		

The mean and S.D. of executive function are 93.72 and 8.495, whereas the mean and S.D. of academic success are 350.13 and 43.373 respectively. The correlation between executive function and academic success of tribal adolescent girls is 0.131. This means there exists a very negligible relationship between executive function and the academic success of tribal adolescent girls (Aggarwal, 2004). Further, when tested for their significance with 194 degrees of freedom, the correlation coefficient was found not to be significant. Hence, the null hypothesis *“There will be a positive relationship between executive function and the academic success of tribal adolescent girls”* is rejected, and it can be interpreted that the relationship is not significant between the variables.

Findings of the Study

The correlation coefficient between executive function and academic success among tribal adolescents is 0.128, which shows a statistically significant relation between executive function and academic success, which conforms with the previous studies (Bull et al., 2008; Clark et al., 2010; Monette et al., 2011; Kim et al., 2013; Sasser et al., 2015; Viterbori et al., 2015; De Franchis et al., 2017; Morgan et al., 2019; Simanowski & Krajewski, 2019; Nakamichi et al., 2021; Coelho et al., 2020; Gunzenhauser & Nückles, 2021; Beisly et al., 2020; Clements et al., 2020). The correlation coefficient between cognitive flexibility and academic success of tribal adolescents is found to be 0.059 which shows no statistically significant relation between both the variables. The coefficient of correlation between working memory and academic success of tribal adolescents is found to be 0.168. The analysis shows a negligible correlation between working memory and academic success, which indicates that working memory has a minimal direct impact on the academic success of tribal adolescents, which is also supported by previous studies (Krumm et al., 2008; Alloway & Alloway, 2010; Swanson & Alloway, 2012; Lee et al., 2013; Friso-van den Bos et al., 2013; Peng et al., 2016; Borella &

de Ribaupierre, 2014; Pham & Hasson, 2014). The coefficient of correlation between inhibition control and academic success of tribal adolescents is found to be 0.028 which shows no statistically significant relation between both the variables. The correlation between executive function and academic success of tribal adolescent boys is 0.21. The analysis shows a low but positive relation between executive function and academic success of tribal adolescent boys, which is also supported by (Sousa et al., 2023). The correlation between executive function and academic success of tribal adolescent girls is 0.131 which shows no statistically significant relation between both the variables.

Education Implications

Schools can incorporate activities that are specially designed to help students, including cognitive flexibility, working memory, and inhibition control. Memory games, problem-solving exercises, and planned organizational tasks will fall under this category. Teachers may undergo training to help students develop executive function skills and understand the importance of these talents. Professional development can include strategies for incorporating executive function exercises into regular courses. Workshops for parents' awareness can be planned to assist parents in understanding the importance of executive functions and foster their children's development at home. Schools can provide resources for mental health care since mental health affects executive function and academic success. This can include stress management seminars, mindfulness training, and counseling services. Regular evaluations to monitor the development of executive function skills and academic progress aligned with appropriate teaching strategies can improve both executive function and academic success. In addition to this the students may be provided with feedback that will address their academic success and helps them to understand and develop their executive function skills.

Conclusion

To sum up, academic success is greatly influenced by executive function as a whole and more specifically by its working memory component. In this context, the schools must ensure a conducive environment essential for promoting different components of executive function with a special focus on working memory. Earlier research studies reveal that adolescents can also greatly benefit from appropriate interventions and instructional strategies that help them improve their executive function skills ultimately contributing to academic success. Furthermore, extensive quantitative and qualitative research can be conducted across the levels and variables to explain and explore the dynamics of the relationship between executive

function and academic success. It will assist in getting a better understanding of executive function and academic success factors among the tribal adolescents of India.

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